

NEW UZBEKISTAN, A NEW OUTLOOK

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Humanity has been interested in the problems of society's development since ancient times. After all, striving for perfection is the most important and vital necessity of the human race. There is a human race that always wants to live better tomorrow than today, to live a fuller life. Therefore, the ways and problems of achieving this have always been one of the eternal concerns of mankind throughout its history. Naturally, there have been countless attempts to find different solutions to this problem in different periods. Rather than the extent to which these efforts served the common purpose, it would be more accurate to say that what was most important to mankind was his dissatisfaction with the life he was passing, and therefore his earnest effort to find the most effective solution to this. Ancient history testifies to the same. A closer look at it clearly confirms that humanity has tried many different approaches to accelerate development, from increasing the role of individuals to achieving drastic changes through revolutionary efforts.

Although there are actually many factors that can affect the development of society, among them there is one factor that is of great importance for the development and development of humanity, and ignoring it is in a sense tantamount to betraying this development. Here we are talking about the role of scientific ideas and theories created with the help of human mind and thinking in the development of society. Because "such universal achievements, which are the great result of the potential of one people ... will become bright pages of human history, give a great impetus to the development of world civilization" [1;5]. For the same reason, today the leader of our country seriously puts the need to create the foundations of the Third Renaissance in the development of New Uzbekistan.

A look into the distant past allows us to cite many vivid examples to confirm our point. In particular, the law of Archimedes about the displacement of a liquid equal to its volume when a body is immersed in a liquid filled with a container, which he discovered while taking a bath, has served the development of mankind happily for centuries. If Pythagoras had not discovered his famous theorem for right triangles, today's modern builder would have been scratching his head without being able to cover the roof of his building. And the laws of thinking discovered by Aristotle in ancient times are still teaching people to think and speak logically.

Fortunately, thinkers who came from our land, which claims to be the cradle of world civilization, and made a great contribution to the development of science, have been active in our motherland in all periods of history. It is extremely proud for today's generation. For example, the scientific views of astrophysics of Ahmad Fergani (797-861), known worldwide as Alfraganus, are not only the product of theoretical observations, but also a scientific picture of the universe created as a result of direct research and observations, as a result of repeated tests and comparisons extremely reliable information about it still arouses the great interest of world scientists.

Also, Ahmad Fergani's activities related to the design and construction of the "Nilometr" to measure the water level on the Nile River, his efforts to implement its practical use, his scientific potential and knowledge spent on this path are also highly praised, and this is a great legacy. The excellent water measuring facility is being carefully preserved as an ancient and rare monument of the past culture of not only the Arab people, but also the entire humanity. As a symbol of gratitude to the honor of our compatriot, who left such an indelible mark in the history of science and culture, the presence of an area called "Uzbekiya" in the capital of Egypt, and the fact that a magnificent statue of our compatriot Ahmad Farghani is standing in Cairo is a sign of deep recognition and respect for this great representative of the First Renaissance.

It is worth noting that the period of spiritual renaissance, which occupies a worthy place in the history of our country, is worthy of attention because of the birth of a great dynasty of scientists and thinkers who made a great contribution to the development of science and culture. During the First Renaissance, Muhammad Khorezmi, Farabi, Beruni, Ibn Sina, etc. made an incomparable contribution to the development of secular sciences such as philosophy, logic, mathematics, geography, astronomy, history, medicine. For example, the science of modern algebra is directly related to the name of our compatriot Khorezmi, while Pharaobi was named the “Second Master” for his great contribution to the development of the fields of learning the philosophy of ancient times, translating the works of Greek philosophers, creating original centuries, and further developing the science of logic, along with informing the peoples of the East in detail got a name. It was during this period that all mankind became aware of the fact that the Earth is spherical thanks to the scientific conclusion of Abu Rayhan Beruni. Beruni, who predicted the existence of a new continent unknown to mankind five centuries before Christopher Columbus, entered history as our grandfather. For example, the science of modern algebra is directly related to the name of our compatriot Khorezmi, while Pharaobi was named the “Second Master” for his great contribution to the development of the fields of learning the philosophy of ancient times, translating the works of Greek philosophers, creating original centuries, and further developing the science of logic, along with informing the peoples of the East in detail got a name. It was during this period that all mankind became aware of the fact that the Earth is spherical thanks to the scientific conclusion of Abu Rayhan Beruni. Beruni, who predicted the existence of a new continent unknown to making five centuries before Cristopher Columbus, entered history as our grandfather.

It should also be noted that the development of this period is not limited to the development of worldly sciences, but the development of Sufism also improved in many aspects during this period. In other words, we are not a nation that has accepted the religion of Islam since the Middle Ages and simply believe in its teachings, but we are a nation that has made a worthy contribution to the theoretical development of the foundations of Islam during the past periods. Our great compatriot scholars like Hakim Termizi and Imam Bukhari developed the field of Hadith science at a high level in Islamic teachings, while Najmuddin Kubra, Ahmed Yassavi, Bahavuddin Naqshbandi enriched the science of tariqat with new and perfect leeches, so that the whole Muslim world still appreciates their views they are putting their faith with respect and reverence.

The Second Renaissance, which was founded during the reign of our grandfather Amir Temur, also delivered thinkers who made a worthy contribution to the development of science. In this, of course, the great patronage of Sohigiron in the development of science and culture, urban planning and crafts in our country played a decisive role. Cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Shahrisabz flourished as huge cultural centers and attracted the attention of foreign tourists. All conditions were created to strengthen the position of the Great Silk Road that passed from Asia to Europe. As a result, by this time, due to the strength and power of the Timurid state, the long-lasting crisis situation caused by the Mongol invasion ended, and a new era in the rise of science and culture was observed in Movarounnahr. Fields of science such as history, astronomy, mathematics, public administration, political science, literature, and linguistics developed rapidly. Great people like Mirza Ulug'bek, Ali Kushchi, Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur founded a new renaissance period in the history of our nation.

Our grandfather Amir Temur raised the field of public administration to the level of art and science. Mirzo Ulugbek devoted his whole life to raise the honor and honor of the Timurid Dynasty to the highest and at the same time made an immortal contribution to the development of the world science of catastrophes due to the theoretical and practical development of the science of astronomy. On the facade of the Faculty of Astronomy of Lomonosov State University, there is a picture of Ulugbek among the great astronomers of the world around Urania, the goddess of the sky, which is a clear evidence of the high level of science and culture of this period.

In this period, Mir Alisher Navai was one of the lifelong artists of words, whose artistic genius was beyond the limits of spatial and temporal dimensions, who had a huge and effective

influence on the development of the culture of our nation and people. “If we call this great person a saint, he is the saint of saints, if we say a thinker, he is the thinker of thinkers, if we say a poet, he is the sultan of poets” [2:47]. After all, Alisher Navai conquered this world with a pen, which conquerors could not take with a sword. However, it is no exaggeration to say that the creative heritage left by our grandfather is equally valuable for all Turkic and Persian-speaking peoples, and it has been inspiring the entire people of Kalam for more than five centuries.

In the world development, there are not many artists who carried out royal affairs in harmony with poetry. But the fact that Zahiriddin Babur has a worthy place among them is both pride and pride for each of us. This unique person, who was subjected to many hardships and trials by the cruel fate, until the last breath of his life, created a fruitful work in the love of the motherland, love for the Motherland, yearning for the soil of his ancestors, wrote beautiful ghazals and occupied an indelible place in the history and heart of our people. The work “Boburnoma” is not only an indication of the great creativity of our grandfather’s thinking, but it is also a great example of his desire to leave a rare source for future generations to learn about music. Its use allows today’s generations to form the most reliable image of that time.

Our nation has a very rich and long history. His past is like a flowing river. And the flowing river will not stop flowing, its beds will never disappear.

By the years of independence, great opportunities arose in the development of our motherland. Uzbekistan began to face the world again. Having chosen its own model of national development, it is taking a bold step towards taking its rightful place in the world community. In particular, the wide-ranging reforms and creative works carried out under the leadership of the President of our country Sh.M. Mirziyoev during the following years increase the confidence of our people in the future and at the same time increase the interest of the world community towards New Uzbekistan.

A number of aspects are typical for the development of today’s world, the processes of globalization are increasing, and competition is intensifying, attracting everyone’s attention. While developed countries are capturing the consumer market by producing more and better products, they are seriously confused about how to produce it. That is, the wider introduction of innovative technologies, it can be safely said, is becoming the main factor of material and spiritual production.

Naturally, even independent Uzbekistan cannot develop without these factors. Therefore, the leader of our country is paying great attention to the further development of science, which is the basis of innovative development. In this regard, as President Sh. M. Mirziyayev himself has emphasized: “Today, updates in this direction require new views and approaches to the issues of taking into account the requirements of the time, creating a new image of the science of our society in the process of implementing reforms and achieving the effectiveness of the dynamics of changes in this area” [1; 246].

As the leader of our country said, creating the foundations of the Third Renaissance to build New Uzbekistan is a responsible task facing the modern young generation. For this, every person who is indifferent and not indifferent to the future and prospects of our country should carefully master the achievements of modern science, master advanced technologies, constantly improve his intellectual potential, have enough knowledge and potential to conduct fundamental research and research, and in every way deeply To be a thinker who can think, he must strive hard. Our country, which has given great scientists and scholars to the world civilization, has all the conditions for bringing up new Fergani’s and Beruni’s, Ulugbek’s and Navai.

Here’s a little lyrical digression. One day, the ruler who sentenced the great orator Cicero, the historian and philosopher of ancient Egypt to death, saw his grandson reading the book of his ideological enemy. In this case, the contribution from the story is that it is impossible not to recognize the people who sacrificed for their country, even their enemies [3;94].

Therefore, we think that the reality of today’s New Uzbekistan requires us to be so selfless for the development of our country, and therefore, only in this way will the riverbeds that flowed never disappear. Maybe it will last forever.

References:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh. New Uzbekistan strategy. T., "Uzbekistan" publishing house. 2021.
2. Karimov I. High spirituality is an inexhaustible power. T., "Spirituality". 2008.
3. Stop I. The orator who conquered Rome. "Tafakkur" magazine. 2001, No. 3.